

Supplemental Materials: Scaling of Earthquake Memory for Interevent Times and Distances

The dynamic of the ETAS model is known as a stochastic space-time point process. In the ETAS model, seismic events are assumed to involve a Poisson process where the conditional intensity function λ is controlled by a few estimated parameters [S1, S2] as follows,

$$\lambda(t|H_t) = \mu + A \sum_{t_i < t} \exp(\alpha(M_i - M_0)) \left(1 + \frac{t - t_i}{c}\right)^{-p}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where H_t is the history process before time t , t_i are the times of the past events and M_i are their magnitudes. The parameter μ is the background event rate, $A = K/c^p$ is the occurrence rate of earthquakes in the Omori law at zero lag, c , p and K are the Omori law parameters, and α is the productivity parameter. The function $\lambda(t|H_t)$ is the probability at time t for the occurrence of an earthquake with a magnitude threshold above M_0 , given the earthquake history H_t . Each event's magnitude is selected independently from the Gutenberg–Richter distribution. The branching ratio n is the average number of events triggered by each event. It can be obtained by integrating $A \exp(\alpha M) \left(1 + \frac{t}{c}\right)^{-p}$ over both time and magnitude from 0 to ∞ and is given by $n = \frac{Ac}{p-1} \frac{\beta}{\beta-\alpha}$, where $\beta = b \ln 10$ ($b = 1$ on the Gutenberg–Richter law). To avoid ETAS model's singularities and to have physical stability, one assumed $0 < n < 1$, such that $p > 1$, $\alpha < \beta$ and $n < 1$ [S3]. The model's parameters were estimated for the Italian catalog and are $\mu = 0.2$, $A = 6.26$, $p = 1.13$, $c = 0.007$ and $\alpha = 1.5$.

The spatial coordinates x and y of earthquakes in the ETAS model can be obtained independently. the conditional intensity $\lambda(x, y, t|H_t)$ can be integrated using spatial coordinates x and y to get the total conditional intensity for the entire region that is equal to the temporal one. Thus, times and spatial coordinates can be obtained separately [S4]: (i) times are calculated for the entire region by Eq. (2); (ii) then we choose spatial coordinates in the region for the events. For simplicity, spatial background events' are assumed to be spatially random. Spatial aftershock events' coordinates x and y are obtained using a spatial kernel function [S5]:

$$f(x - x_i, y - y_i, M_i) = \frac{q - 1}{\pi D \zeta(M_i)} \left(1 + \frac{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2}{D \zeta(M_i)}\right)^{-q}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$\zeta(M_i) = \exp[\gamma_m (M_i - M_0)], \quad (\text{S3})$$

where i represents the triggering event; q , D and γ_m are the estimated parameters. In the present study the value of these parameters are $q = 1.66$, $D = 0.001$ and $\gamma_m = 0.64$ for the Italian catalog; these were estimated using the maximum likelihood estimator [S5].

We next show here further supporting material (mainly figures) which are quoted the main manuscript.

[S1] S. Touati, M. Naylor, and I. G. Main, Phys. Rev. Lett. **102**, 168501 (2009).

[S2] J. Fan, D. Zhou, L. M. Shekhtman, A. Shapira, R. Hofstetter, W. Marzocchi, Y. Ashkenazy, and S. Havlin, Phys. Rev. E **99**, 042210 (2019), 1807.10497.

[S3] D. Sornette and A. Helmstetter, Phys. Rev. Lett. **89**, 158501 (2002).

[S4] S. Touati, M. Naylor, I. G. Main, and M. Christie, J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth **116**, B03304 (2011).

[S5] J. Zhuang, Res. Geophys. **2**, 8 (2012).

FIG. S1. The number of earthquakes N as a function of magnitude larger than or equal to the magnitude threshold M_0 . The dashed line represents the Gutenberg-Richter law $\log_{10}N(m \geq M_0) \propto -bM_0$, $b = 1$.

FIG. S2. Spatial distribution of Italian earthquake catalog between 1981 and 2017 for the magnitude threshold 3.0. Blue boxes cover the areas 1 and 2.

FIG. S3. Time series of interevent (a) times and (c) distances from area 1 of Fig. S2. (b),(d) Same as (a),(c) but for area 2 of Fig. S2.

FIG. S4. Time series (a), (c) for the time and distance similar to Figure 1 of the main text but for the Japanese catalog. (b), (d) correspond to the California catalog. The dashed lines represent the earthquakes with magnitudes above 6.0.

FIG. S5. Scatter plot of the interevent times versus interevent distances for the results in Figure 1 of the main text for all Italy. One can see well separated two blobs suggesting that the lower one (in τ and r) represents aftershocks while the higher represent main shocks.

FIG. S6. (Color online) Conditional PDF of (a) the interevent times τ_{50} and (b) the interevent distances r_{50} for the entire Italy and magnitude threshold $M_0 = 3.0$; the common area between the first and third quantiles is $s_{13} = 0.70$ and $s_{13} = 0.78$ for times and distances. (c),(d) Same as (a),(b) but for lag $k = 100$ where the common area is $s_{13} = 0.76$ and $s_{13} = 0.80$ for times and distances respectively.

FIG. S7. (Color online) Conditional PDF of (a) the shuffled interevent times τ_1 (the common area is $s_{13} = 0.969 \pm 0.007$ which is calculated from the 10^3 realizations) and (b) the shuffled interevent distances r_1 , ($s_{13} = 0.9734 \pm 0.007$) for the shortest one-third quantile $Q1$ and longest quantile $Q3$. The black dashed curves depict the PDF for all τ . The different PDF are almost identical.

FIG. S8. (Color online) Conditional PDF of (a) the interevent times τ_1 and (b) the interevent distances r_1 for grid size $L = 3.5^\circ$ and magnitude threshold $M_0 = 3.0$; the common area between the first and third quantiles is $s_{13} = 0.31$ and $s_{13} = 0.45$ for times and distances. (c),(d) Same as (a),(b) but for lag $k = 10$ where the common area is $s_{13} = 0.48$ and $s_{13} = 0.71$ for times and distances respectively.

FIG. S9. (Color online) The average of the standard variation of the scaling curves in Figs. 3c, d of the main text as a function of the parameters a and d_u for (a) the interevent times and (b) interevent distances. The presented minimization is used to find the optimal scaling parameters, shown in Figs. 3c and 3d of the main text.

FIG. S10. (Color online) The average of time differences between two earthquakes with the lag k as a function of k (a) before scaling and (b) after scaling for the different grid sizes L (colors) and different magnitude thresholds M_0 (shapes). The red curves deviate from the linear curves at large k for the small grid size $L = 3.5^\circ$, since there is not enough events in some boxes. Slope of the black dashed line is equal to 1. Thus there is the relation $k 10^{-bM_0} \propto \langle t_{i+k} - t_i \rangle L^{d_f}$, where $d_f = 1.7$ is the fractal dimension found by Bak et al. in ref (4) of the main text.

FIG. S11. (Color online) Japanese catalog memory measure (a) $S(\tau_k|\tau_0)$ (interevent times) and (b) $S(r_k|r_0)$ (interevent distances) as a function of the lag index k . Colors represent different grid sizes L . Shapes represent different magnitude thresholds M_0 . $L = 18^\circ$ covers the whole region for Japan catalog. Rescaled memory measure for (c) interevent times and (d) interevent distances. Black dashed lines are fitted power-law curves (which look linear on a log-log plot). The vertical red dotted line indicates the location of the crossover.

FIG. S12. (Color online) Same as Fig. S11 for the California catalog. $L = 12^\circ$ covers the whole region for California catalog.

FIG. S13. (Color online) Conditional PDF of (a) the interevent times τ_1 and (b) the interevent distances r_1 ($M_0 = 3.0$) for the ETAS model; the common area between the first and third quantiles is $s_{13} = 0.61$ and $s_{13} = 0.70$ for times and distances respectively. (c),(d) Same as (a),(b) but for lag $k = 10$ where the common area is $s_{13} = 0.80$ and $s_{13} = 0.92$ times and distances respectively. The model's parameters are $\mu = 0.2$, $A = 6.26$, $p = 1.13$, $c = 0.07$ and $\alpha = 1.5$. The spatial model's parameters are $D = 0.001$, $q = 1.66$ and $\gamma_m = 0.64$. Note the relatively large common area, especially for lag $k = 10$, in contrast to the smaller common area found in the real catalogs (see Fig. 2 of the main text).

FIG. S14. (Color online) ETAS model power-law exponents γ_1 (upper panels), γ_2 (middle panels) and exponent ratio γ_2/γ_1 (bottom panels) of the memory measure for the interevent times. The remaining ETAS model parameters are $A = 6.26$ and $c = 0.07$. Different columns present the results for different background noise level μ . The ranges of the p and α are limited by the branching ratio n .

FIG. S15. (Color online) Same as Fig. S14 for interevent distances. In contrast to Fig. S14 (interevent times), the exponents seem to be independent of p .

FIG. S16. (Color online) Memory measure S as a function of the lag index k for (a) interevent times and (b) distances respectively for the real catalog of all Italy (magnitude threshold $M_0 = 3.0$). Colors and shapes represent different time periods.

FIG. S17. (Color online) The memory measure S as a function of the lag index k for (a) interevent times and (b) distances respectively for the simulated catalog generated by the ETAS model where the length of the simulated catalogs is the same as the real catalog of Italy. Colors and shapes represent different magnitude thresholds. The memory measure S is averaged over 50 independent realizations. The error bars indicate the standard deviation.